

Synthesis and Reactions of some 3-Substituted-[5,6]benzocoumarins

G. S. S. MURTHI* and M. BASAK

Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal, P. O. North Bengal University, Darjeeling-734 430

Manuscript received 5 June 1992, revised 6 January 1993, accepted 6 January 1993

The recent reports that some substituted chromenes and their epoxy derivatives possess antijuvenile hormonal properties¹ and cytotoxicity², have prompted us to prepare similar compounds and test their efficacy in pest control. In this connection we needed different coumarins. We report here the synthesis, reactions and spectral properties of ethyl 2-oxonaphtho[1,2-*b*]pyran-3-carboxylate (2) and 3-acetyl-2-oxonaphtho[1,2-*b*]pyran (3).

Results and Discussions

Compounds 2 and 3 were synthesised by the reaction of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (1)³ with diethyl malonate and ethyl acetoacetate respectively, in presence of pyridine and catalytic amount of piperidine (Scheme 1). The pmr (CDCl₃) spectra of both 2 and 3 displayed a singlet peak at δ 9.33 for C-4 hydrogen. The ir spectrum of 2 showed bands due to unsaturated δ -lactonic CO and ester CO at 1 690 and 1 675 cm⁻¹, while 3 showed CO absorptions at 1 655 cm⁻¹.

On gentle reflux in methanolic hydrochloric acid, 2 underwent transesterification to give 4 (84%) while 3 gave only intractable tarry material. Alkaline hydrolysis of 2 with 5% ethanolic NaOH followed by acidification furnished the corresponding carboxylic acid (5) as yellow needles, m.p. 225°. The acid (5) did not undergo decarboxylation even after prolonged boiling with aqueous acid probably because the resulting anion is unstable; furthermore, even if the acid is considered as an α,β -unsaturated acid, decarboxylation⁴ is likely to be difficult because in this case, β,γ -isomerisation is not possible.

The pmr spectrum of 5 exhibited a broad singlet at δ 12.35 ppm (COOH) and in ¹³C nmr (CDCl₃) the two carbonyl carbons appeared at δ 113.4 and 113.8 ppm. In the mass spectrum of 5 the molecular ion appeared at *m/z* 240 (m.f. C₁₄H₈O₄). On the other hand, compound 3 upon treatment with ethanolic NaOH followed by acidification furnished the starting aldehyde (1) (identical with m.p., co-tlc and pmr). In Table 1 are summarised the physical and spectral data of compounds 2–5.

Experimental

[5,6]Benzocoumarins (2 or 3). *General procedure*: A mixture of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (1) and an active methylene compound in the ratio of (1 : 2.5) was dissolved in pyridine (4 ml/mmol of the aldehyde) and catalytic amount of piperidine. The reaction mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 1 h. The resulting dark brown reaction mixture was cooled and poured into crushed ice and then acidified with concentrated HCl. The solid product was washed with ice-cold water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol as yellow needles.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2–5

Compd. no.	M.p °C	Yield %	Spectral data
2	118	84	ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 690, 1 675, 1 628 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 373, 252, 233 nm; pmr δ (CDCl_3/TMS) 1.46 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 4.48 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 7.47 (1H, d, J 8.86 Hz), 7.62 (1H, m, centered at), 7.76 (1H, m, centered at), 7.94 (1H, dd, J 1, 8.1 Hz), 8.11 (1H, d, J 8.86 Hz), 8.33 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 9.33 (1H, s); ^{13}C nmr δ (CDCl_3/TMS) 14.3, 48, 62.1, 112.3, 116.5, 116.7, 121.5, 126.5, 129.1, 129.2, 129.4, 130.2, 136.1, 144.5, 155.96, 163.6; m/z 268 (M^+ ; 29.4), 149 (25), 139 (46.5), 81 (42.3), 69 (100), 43(98)
3	186	86	ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 655, 1 608 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 392, 252, 230 nm; pmr δ (CDCl_3/TMS) 2.79 (3H, s), 7.49 (1H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 7.62 (1H, m, centered at), 7.94 (1H, dd, J 1.3, 7.78 Hz), 8.12 (1H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 8.38 (1H, d, J 8.42 Hz), 9.33 (1H, s); ^{13}C nmr δ (CDCl_3/TMS) 30.7, 112.8, 116.5, 121.7, 122.5, 126.6, 129.2, 129.9, 136.3, 143.3, 156.2, 195.6; m/z 238 (M^+ ; 49.8), 223 (91.8), 139 (100), 43 (52.9)
4	158	81	ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 680, 1 660, 1 638 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 372, 259, 226 nm; pmr δ (CDCl_3/TMS) 4.01 (3H, s), 7.46 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz), 7.62 (1H, m, centered at), 7.75 (1H, m, centered at), 7.92 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 8.20 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz), 8.33 (1H, d, J 8 Hz), 9.33 (1H, s)
5	225	73	ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 400, 1 665 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 315, 322, 252, 233 nm; pmr δ (CDCl_3/TMS) 7.59 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz), 7.71 (1H, m, centered at), 7.65 (1H, m, centered at), 8.01 (1H, d, J 7.6 Hz), 8.26 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz), 8.45 (1H, d, J 8.1 Hz), 9.72 (1H, s), 12.35 (1H, br s); ^{13}C nmr δ (CDCl_3/TMS) 113.4, 113.8, 116.5, 122, 127.6, 129.6, 130.1, 130.4, 138, 147.1, 156, 163.6, 188.6, 194; m/z 240 (M^+ ; 78.4), 196 (50.1), 168 (72.9), 139 (100), 69 (22.5)

Treatment of 2 or 3 with methanolic HCl. General procedure: A solution of 2 or 3 in 5% methanolic HCl (5 ml/mmol of the compound) was refluxed for 3 h. Methanol was then removed under reduced pressure and the solid residue was dissolved in ether. The ether solution was then washed with aqueous NaHCO_3 , brine and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Evaporation of the solvent furnished a yellow solid which was recrystallised from ethanol. In case of 3 the reaction mixture turned deep red during refluxing and after work-up an intractable tarry material was obtained.

Treatment of 2 or 3 with ethanolic NaOH solution. General procedure: A solution 2 or 3 in 5% ethanolic NaOH (10 ml/mmol) was refluxed for 3 h under nitrogen. Ethanol was then removed under reduced pressure and after cooling, the residue was acidified with ice-cold ^3N HCl. The resulting solid was washed with ice-cold water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. Pelayo Camps, Universidad de Barcelona, Spain and Dr. Mitsuo Miyazawa, Kinki University, Japan, and C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for nmr and mass spectra. One of the authors (M.B) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. W. S. BOWERS, T. OHTA, J. S. CLEERE and P. A. MARSELLA, *Science*, 1976, **193**, 542.
2. J. BUJONS, P. CAMPS and A. MESSEQUER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **31**, 5235.
3. A. RUSSEL and L. B. LOCKHART, *Org. Synth.*, 1955, **3**, 463.
4. E. S. GOULD, "Mechanism and Structure in Organic Chemistry", Holt, Rinehart & Winstone, New York, 1966, pp. 151, 352.